

Western blot images for TLR2 and GAPDH in UUO kidneys. Uncropped western blot gel images for TLR2 and GAPDH in neonatal WT kidneys (on day 7 and 14 of life). * marks the section used in Figure 1. TLR2 and GAPDH were visualized separately, but they represent the same gel.

Western blot images for Caspase-8 and GAPDH in Uuo kidneys. Uncropped western blot gel images for Caspase-8 and GAPDH in neonatal WT and TLR2^{-/-} kidneys (on day 7 and 14 of life). * marks the section used in Figure 2. Caspase-8 and GAPDH were visualized separately, but they represent the same gel.

Western blot images for GSDMD and GAPDH in UO kidneys. Uncropped western blot gel images for GSDMD and GAPDH in neonatal WT and TLR2^{-/-} kidneys (on day 7 and 14 of life). * marks the section used in Figure 3. GSDMD and GAPDH were visualized separately (different exposers), but they represent the same gel.

Western blot images for GSDME and GAPDH in UO kidneys. Uncropped western blot gel images for GSDME and GAPDH in neonatal WT and TLR2^{-/-} kidneys (on day 7 and 14 of life). * marks the section used in Figure 3. GSDME and GAPDH were visualized separately (different exposers), but they represent the same gel.

Western blot images for HMGB1 and GAPDH in UUO kidneys. Uncropped western blot gel images for HMGB1 and GAPDH in neonatal WT and TLR2^{-/-} kidneys (on day 7 and 14 of life). * marks the section used in Figure 3.

Western blot images for TNF-α and GAPDH in UUO kidneys.

Uncropped western blot gel images for TNF-α and GAPDH in neonatal WT and TLR2^{-/-} kidneys (on day 7 and 14 of life). * marks the section used in Figure 3. TNF-α and GAPDH were visualized separately (different exposers), but they represent the same gel.

22.4.13 TLR - Projekt Kollektiv 2

gel 1

gel 2

Western blot images for Galectin-3, TGF- β , and GAPDH in UUO kidneys. Uncropped western blot gel images for Galectin-3, TGF- β , and GAPDH in neonatal WT and TLR2^{-/-} kidneys (on day 7 and 14 of life). * marks the section used in Figure 6.

18.4.13

TLR-kollektion 3

2-5 ne

Gel 1

75-

50-

37-

d7 d14 d7 d14 | d7 d14 d7 d14
Sham UO Sham UO
WT TLR2-/-

* SMA
GAPDH
*

Gel 2

75-

50-

37-

d7 d14 d7 d14 | d7 d14 d7 d14
Sham UO Sham UO
WT TLR2-/-

SMA
GAPDH

Western blot images for α -SMA and GAPDH in UO kidneys. Uncropped western blot gel images for α -SMA and GAPDH in neonatal WT and TLR2^{-/-} kidneys (on day 7 and 14 of life). * marks the section used in Figure 6.

Western blot images for MMP-2 and GAPDH in UUO kidneys. Uncropped western blot gel images for MMP-2 and GAPDH in neonatal WT and TLR2^{-/-} kidneys (on day 7 and 14 of life). * marks the section used in Figure 6. MMP-2 and GAPDH were visualized separately (different exposur times), but they represent the same gel.